

Socio-Cultural Symbolisms of Egúngún Costumes Across Six Yoruba Towns: Fostering Contemporary Kindred-Ship from Ancestral Artistic Memories

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ABSTRACT: Egúngún as a Yorùbá masquerade performs across the geopolitical spaces of Yorùbáland. Historically, Egúngún fostered social development in aspects of unity, morality, security and socio-cultural prosperity. The present-day ethical disregard for the social impact of Egúngún and other such cultural legacies are regrettable in society. There is therefore a need to re-enact ancestral memories for contemporary social development. The aesthetics of Egúngún costumes in six Yorùbá towns of Osun State, Nigeria, is the focus of this paper. Masquerade paraphernalia were examined for similarities in iconography, symbolism and social order. The six towns are: Imesi-Ilé, Ile-Ifè, Ejigbo, Ede, Osogbo and Ila-Orangun. These towns were selected because they have contemporary active Egúngún practices. The range of masquerades examined included Ládùnùnwo, Ìyẹkíyẹ, and Gbádó of Imesi-Ilé; Lobanikan and Gbandu of Ile-Ifè; Adinimodo and Owolewa of Ejigbo; Gbájẹ̀rò and Òndòrù of Ede; Òpèlè-Ìbà and Kúndúké of Osogbo, and Èlẹwẹ of Ila-Orangun. The research methodology used was qualitative using field investigation comprising of participant observation, interviews with relevant custodians of the Egúngún traditions, photographic and video recordings, and literature reviews. The comparative analysis of the data was carried out with the theoretical framework of Formalism and Social Realism. Findings reveal that the Egúngún in these communities share structural similarities in layered robes with concealed amulets, colours, headdresses and masking forms, lappets and other forms of ornamentation. These signify shared ancestral migration, communality and exchange. In conclusion, such kindred-ship is a necessary panacea for contemporary social reform. Egúngún in the six towns exhumes positive ancestral memories, creating a continuity needed for development.

KEYWORDS: Costume, Egúngún, Iconography, Kindred-ship, Masquerades, Social Realism

1. INTRODUCTION

The Egúngún tradition stands as one of the most enduring pillars of Yorùbá cultural identity. As ancestral masquerades, Egúngún mediate between the living (ayé) and the ancestral realm (òrun), embodying values that sustain social order. Historically, Egúngún societies served as moral watchdogs, security enforcers, agents of communal unity, and promoters of socio-cultural well-being.

Despite these contributions, modern attitudes shaped by urbanization, globalization, and religious syncretism have marginalized many indigenous practices. As society faces rising issues of moral decline, insecurity, and weakened communal bonds, it becomes important to revisit cultural mechanisms that formerly nurtured collective well-being. This paper positions Egúngún aesthetics as one pathway for re-activating ancestral memories and using such to strengthen contemporary social structures.

Costumes play a central role in Egúngún festivals. These outfits, known as “ago,” “eku,” or “aso,” are always brightly coloured. This is captured in a Yoruba proverb that says, “Onírúurú l’aso Egúngún,” meaning Egúngún garments come in many varieties. The costumes differ in colour, shape, and size, and there are as many types of Egúngún as there are costumes (Campbell, 2016).

This study examined the aesthetics of Egúngún costumes in six Yorùbá towns in Osun State, Nigeria: Imesi-Ilé, Ile-Ifè, Ejigbo, Ede, Osogbo, and Ila-Orangun. These towns host annual festivals featuring both secular and sacred masquerades, each with its own costume designs, performance styles, and ritual functions. These towns were chosen because they maintain active Egúngún traditions in the present day. The masquerades explored in this paper include Ládùnùnwo, Ìyẹkíyẹ, and Gbádó of Imesi-Ilé; Lobanikan and Gbandu of Ile-Ifè; Adinimodo and Owolewa of Ejigbo; Gbájẹ̀rò and Òndòrù of Ede; Òpèlè-Ìbà and Kúndúké of Osogbo; and Èlẹwẹ of Ila-Orangun. Their paraphernalia were analysed for shared elements in iconography, symbolism, and social significance. Adebowale (2020) supports this view, noting that “the physical performance of any Egúngún is driven by the spirits of the ancestors associated with that specific Egúngún, uniting the performer and the Eku, the costume itself. The gradual erosion of traditional cultures has led to the reduced relevance of Egúngún institutions in contemporary Yoruba society. The symbolic, moral, and social functions embedded within Egúngún practices are often misunderstood or dismissed. Consequently, their potentials to inspire unity, moral discipline, and social transformation remain underutilized. This research bridges the gap by exploring how visual and performance elements of Egúngún costumes embody ancestral knowledge capable of informing present-day development.

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Plate 1: Map of Nigeria showing Study area (Osun State).

Source: Computer generated by Joseph Muyiwa Olumoyegun, Cartography and GIS Section, Department of Geography, University of Ibadan, Nigeria (2025).

2. AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to examine the visual forms and icons of Egúngún costumes in six Yorùbá towns of Osun State, Nigeria to identify the various types, similarities and symbolism of Egúngún costumes used in Imesi-Ilé, Ile-Ifè, Ejigbo, Ede, Osogbo, and Ila-Orangun. The objectives were to explore their colours, shapes, and stylistic features for comparison. This will enable masquerade paraphernalia of different Egúngún types to determine similarities in iconography, symbolism, and social significance. In addition, the research investigated how these costumes reflect the cultural beliefs and ancestral connections that guide Egúngún performances.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative methodology complemented by ethnographic and visual analysis. Data were collected from both primary and secondary sources, with the majority obtained from primary fieldwork. This involved participant observations during festival cycles, interviews with elders, cultural custodians, and masquerade performers, as well as photographic and video documentation of costume components. Particular attention was given to the “ẹkú Egúngún” and its associated paraphernalia. Ethical permission for the research was granted by the communities’ kings, who serve as the custodians of their local cultural heritage. Supplementary data were gathered through library and archival research on Yorùbá masquerades and other related literature. Visual materials including dresses, headpieces, amulets, appliqué, ornaments, and layered textile ensemble were analysed for their artistic and symbolic significance. A comparative analytical approach was used to examine similarities and differences across the six towns. The masquerades studied include Ládùnúnwo, Ìyẹkíiyẹ, and Gbádó (Imesi-Ilé); Lobanikan and Gbandu (Ile-Ifè); Adanimodo and Owolewa (Ejigbo); Gbájẹ̀ẹ̀rò and Òndòrù (Ede); Òpẹ̀lẹ̀-Ìbà and Kúndúkẹ (Osogbo); and Èlẹ̀wẹ (Ila-Orangun).

4. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The comparative analysis of the data was carried out with the theoretical framework of Formalism and Social Realism because the images studied apart from being artistic are religious and socio-cultural. These frameworks provided detailed explanations of the ẹkú, colour symbolism, material paraphernalia, and carved wood objects used in the masking culture of egúngún within the six towns in the study. The theories foster a critical investigation and explanation of the meaning and similarities of each image represented in the paraphernalia. In analysing Egúngún costumes, this study employs both formalist and social realist frameworks to capture their aesthetic and socio-cultural dimensions. The formalist lens focuses on the material composition of the costumes, examining elements such as textile layering, ornamentation, masking structures, and chromatic patterns, thereby highlighting the artistic sophistication and craftsmanship involved. Complementing this, the perspective of social realism interpreted how these visual features encode communal values, social norms, historical migration patterns, kinship networks, and moral principles, reflecting the broader cultural context in which the masquerades operate. By integrating these two approaches, the study demonstrates that Egúngún costumes function not only as objects of visual and aesthetic display but also as dynamic agents of social cohesion, cultural memory, and spiritual engagement within Yorùbá society.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Egúngún costumes demonstrate exceptional diversity in shape, style, and aesthetic composition. Some masquerades feature towering structures that emphasize authority, while others employ layered textiles that move rhythmically during performance. Colour symbolism plays a major role: red often signifies vitality and power; white represents purity, ancestral presence, and spiritual elevation; black conveys mystery and protective energy; and multicoloured designs symbolize abundance and communal unity. Iconography includes embroidered motifs, geometric patterns, cowries, metallic charms, and amulets, each carrying meanings related to cosmology, lineage identity, and spiritual protection.

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Èkú Egúngún Ládùnùnwo, Ìyẹkíyẹ, and Gbàdó of Imesi-Ilé

In an interview with Pa Emmanuel Sunday Tawode (81 years, personal communication, March 18, 2025), the chief custodian of Egúngún in Imesi-Ilé. Pa. Tawode explains that the origin of Egúngún Ládùnùnwo, Ìyẹkíyẹ, and Gbàdó in Imesi-Ilé can be traced to the Otu-Okò family. The Otu-Okò family migrated into Imesi-Ilé from Òyó-Ìgbòhò, at the beginning of the 17th century (Smith, 1965). The family relocated to Imesi-Ilé, due to their opposition to the proposal of Aláàfin Ogboolu to move back to Old Oyo. When the family broke off from Òyó-Ìgbòhò they wandered until they got to Imesi-Ilé. On getting to Imesi-Ile, they were warmly welcomed with their Egúngún. Pa. Tawode noted there had been other local Egúngún in Imesi-Ile before the arrival of the Otu-Okò family, who brought Ládùnùnwo from Ìgbòhò, over time, after arriving Imesi-Ilé the family later introduced the other two Egúngún Ìyẹkíyẹ and Gbàdó. Ìyẹkíyẹ and Gbàdó were introduced due to the wide acceptance of Ládùnùnwo.

Each of the three Egúngún possesses a distinctive “èkú”, with variations in materials, colours, and iconographic symbolism. The “èkú” of Ládùnùnwo, for example, consists of a wooden helmet mask and predominantly white attire. Most of the costume is rendered in white fabric, including the mask, except for the hair section, which is painted black to symbolize eternal youth (Plate 1). Additional elements, such as the collar around the neck and the straps used to secure the lower part of the costume to the wearer, are also crafted from black cloth strips. The “èkú” is typically kept in the Egúngún grove (ìgbàlẹ). The carved helmet masks are designed as either male or female (Plate 2) and often feature facial markings on the cheeks. These marks, measuring approximately six to seven centimeters, are arranged vertically or horizontally in rows or columns, and are traditionally worn by members of the Otu-Okò family.

Other paraphernalia associated with the Ládùnùnwo “èkú” include two black horsewhips, machetes, swords, red velvet fabrics, white apparel, and the “Àgan”. The appearance of Egúngún Ládùnùnwo is the most revered in Imesi-Ilé. Both male and female masquerades are considered representatives of the spirits of ancestral mates manifesting in physical form (Plate 3) and are typically dressed in white “èkú”. When they emerge, they move together as a pair, symbolizing unity and the spiritual bond of the ancestors.

Plate 2: Both male and female Egúngún Ládùnùnwo in their full costume performing before their audience.
Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

Plate 3: Èkú Ládùnùnwo at the secret grove (ìgbàlẹ),
Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

Plate 4: Egúngún Ládùnùnwo move around together as a couple, symbolizing unity and the spiritual bond of the ancestors.
Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

Egúngún Ìyékíiyẹ derives its name from a distinctive part of its “ẹkú” made from a collection of feathers, known in Yorùbá as “iyé”, meaning “all sorts of feathers.” This masquerade ranks immediately after Ládùnùnwo in precedence. While Ládùnùnwo was brought from Oyo, Igboho originating from where the Otu-Okò family migrated to Imesi-Ilé Ìyékíiyẹ and Gbádó, though also part of the Otu-Okò lineage, were initiated after the family’s settlement in Imesi-Ilé.

The costume of Ìyékíiyẹ features a red conical headpiece adorned at the top with feathers from various birds. Both the red conical cap and the feathers symbolize royalty and reflect its association with people of all races and colours. A face veil, knitted with sufficiently large air holes for breathing and visibility, is often incorporated. The veil is typically patterned with horizontal strips in red, green, and blue. The rest of the costume consists of an overall suit woven with broad wine and purple Aso Oke. At the back, a large loose covering dangles freely, adding volume and movement to the masquerade. Ìyékíiyẹ carries a machete as a symbol of its martial authority and capacity to wage war.

Plate 5: Egúngún Ìyékíiyẹ standing on ancient stone of authority at king’s palace
Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

A distinguishing feature of Gbádó is its mask, carved in the form of a human face. The mask displays a woven hairdo painted black, facial scarification marks on the cheeks, and black-painted lips. Although these features suggest a female figure, the owners of the Egúngún refer to it simply as “ẹrù” (load) Egúngún. When this load is attached to the outer “ẹkú”, the masquerade may temporarily remove it and continue the performance without it. Around the mask, woven sack is arranged to resemble a braided hairstyle, extending outward and adding volume around the wearer’s head. The costume of Gbádó consists of a flowing, full-length gown in Aso Oke fabric, covering the entire body also wearing modern purple socks with black stripes (see Plate 5). All parts of the costume are cream, except for the top of the head, which is painted black to signify eternal youth, similar to the symbolism in Ládùnùnwo.

Plate 6: Egúngún Gbádo with entourage and close shot of headdress (Imesi-Ilé)
Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

Egúngún Lobanikan and Gbandu of Ile Ife

Ile-Ife, often referred to as the cradle of the Yoruba race, is a historic town in southwestern Nigeria, located in present-day Osun State. It has a deep cultural and spiritual significance, with a history dating back to between the 7th and 10th centuries AD (Biobaku, 1955). The city is famous for its ancient Yoruba civilization, naturalistic bronze and terracotta sculptures, and unique traditional practices.

Egúngún masquerades in Ile-Ife play a vital role in honoring ancestors and preserving Yoruba traditions. While many deities exist within the city, only a few have a widespread following. Two major festivals, Olojo and Edi, are celebrated by the entire community, whereas others, such as Egúngún Lobanikan, and Gbandu are performed in more localized settings, particularly at Enuwa in Ile-Ife. According to costumier Eludini Segun, these Egúngún masquerades each have distinct characteristics and symbolic roles. Egúngún Lobanikan is a highly revered and powerful masquerade associated with spiritual authority and ancestral power. Its elaborate headdress consists of layer of calabash, and richly coloured fabrics. Lobanikan performs sacred dances during festivals, such as Olojo, to invoke spiritual protection and blessings. Similarly, Egúngún Lobanikan and Ládùnùnwo of Imesi-Ilé has some similarities in terms of their headdresses but a different fabric outfits.

Egúngún Gbandu represent a warrior spirit, Gbandu embodies bravery and strength. It is believed to protect the community from evil force which speaks of security as it is necessary globally in modern times. The costume is fierce and intimidating, featuring bold colours like red, black, and gold on the wooden headdress roped with coconut leaves on white apparel also holding a hand fan symbolizing authority. Similarly, in terms of wooden headdress with tribal marks Gbandu is compared to Egúngún Ládùnùnwo and Lobanikan. Egúngún Gbandu leads purification rituals and engages in ceremonial dances emphasizing protection.

Plate 7: Egúngún Lobanikan of Ile Ife
Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

Plate 8: Egúngún Gbandu (Ile Ife)
Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

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Egúngún Òpélé-Ìbà and Kúndúke of Osogbo

One of the most renowned masquerades in Osogbo is Òpélé-Ìbà, which originated as a symbolic gift to a prince from the Láròyè family. Today, Òpélé-Ìbà remains a distinguished royal masquerade, making an annual visit to the king's palace, where it is received with great honor by the royal family. Local variations are equally significant. For example, the Egúngún Òpélé-Ìbà and kúndúke of Osogbo tends toward refined, elegant textile layering, while those of Ede emphasize flamboyant displays designed to captivate audiences. Despite these differences, all towns share the core belief that the costume transforms the performer into a spiritual vessel. As Adebowale (2020) notes, 'the physical performance of any Egúngún is propelled by the spirits of the ancestors, uniting the performer with the eku (costume).' This reinforces the idea that aesthetics and spirituality are inseparable in Egúngún practice. Egúngún Òpélé-Ìbà and kúndúke of Osogbo similarly has headdress like that of Gbado of Imesi-Ilé (Plate 5). Although, different apparel and colours.

Plate 9: Egúngún Òpélé-Ìbà of Osogbo performing at king's palace
Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

Plate10: Egúngún kúndúke of Osogbo
Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

Eégún Èlẹ̀wẹ̀ of Ila-Orangun

Ila-Orangun has long been recognized for its deep-rooted traditional religious practices and sociocultural heritage. Historically, the town was rich in various forms of traditional worship and indigenous festivals dedicated to deities such as Ogun, Sango, Oro, Oya, Osun, Obatala, and Egúngún (Adebayo, 2015 p.3). It is common for almost every compound to have a deity (Orisa) to which offerings and obeisance are made monthly (ibid). Among the many social and religious festivities in Ila-Orangun, the Egúngún masquerade holds a prominent place.

A unique and notable form of Egúngún in Ila-Orangun is the Èlẹ̀wẹ̀ masquerade, which is distinguished by its vibrant and artistically significant costumes, reflecting the deep artistic traditions of the Yoruba people. Research indicates that Èlẹ̀wẹ̀ serves as an entertainment masquerade and is celebrated alongside other Egúngún to mark their festival. According to an oral interview with Chief Ajiroba, Egún Èlẹ̀wẹ̀ is traditionally celebrated every three years between June and August. Ila-Orangun is regarded as the originator of Egún Èlẹ̀wẹ̀ in the Igbomina region. This is further affirmed by an oral interview with Oba Abdul-Raheem Adeoti Adewale Akolade, the Olomu of Omu-Aran, as well as testimonies from Ila-Orangun citizens, who recognize Egún Èlẹ̀wẹ̀ as an essential cultural identity of all Igbomina people.

Plate 11: Egúngún Elewe of Ila Orangun dancing barefooted with Bature a variety of colourful threads compose of aesthetic elements capable of attracting people.

Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

Gbá jèèrò and Òndòru of Ede

Ede is a prominent Yoruba town in present-day Osun State, southwestern Nigeria. Historically, it was established as an Oyo military outpost in the 15th century under the leadership of an Oyo warrior-prince and a skilled archer (Oyeweso, 2002, p.100). Today, Ede has expanded to include neighboring communities such as Sekona, Oloki, Alajue, and Owode, among others.

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A unique and mystical tradition in Ede is the belief in the return of a dead king's spirit, which manifests in the beating of the state drum. This phenomenon is regarded as an overwhelming spiritual event that must be addressed through rituals and sacrifices. It is widely believed that Timì Kubolaje, a historical ruler of Ede, became one of the revered ancestral spirits (èégún òlá) worshipped in the town today.

One of the most significant figures in Ede's Egúngún (masquerade) tradition is Gbá Jèèró, a highly revered masquerade who takes center stage during the annual Egúngún Festival. Gbá Jèèró, whose name means "the hanger of witches." He is often summoned when evil deeds or acts of witchcraft are suspected in the community. Gbá Jèèró is believed to have the supernatural ability to identify witches and criminals, serving as a form of traditional law enforcement. Similar roles exist in other towns, such as the Egúngún Iyékíyè of Imesi-Ilé.

Plate 12: Egúngún Gbá jèèró of Ede with entourage Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

Òndòrú known for his fierce demeanor, Òndòrú carries a powerful club and is always accompanied by followers (Atónà-Èégún) wielding whips and canes. His presence causes great excitement and fear among the townspeople, as he is known for his playful yet intimidating interactions even striking the Timì during his visits to the palace, symbolizing his supreme authority.

Plate 13: Egúngún Òndòrú of Ede Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

Despite the historical and cultural significance of Egúngún in Ede, many masquerades have fallen into extinction due to the spread of Islam and Christianity, as well as modernization and urbanization. As Prince Adewale Laoye notes, many traditions have faded because family heads responsible for certain masquerades failed to pass down knowledge to their offspring. With no one left to continue the lineage, several Egúngún traditions have disappeared.

Today, the Egúngún cult is dominated by older men struggling to preserve these customs against the encroaching influences of foreign religions and modern lifestyles.

EGÚNGÚN ADINIMODO, OWOLEWA OF EJIGBO

Ejigbo is a major Yoruba town in Osun State, Nigeria, located approximately 40 kilometers from Osogbo, the state capital. In the 1963 Nigerian census, its population was recorded at 46,000, with a landmass of 25 square kilometers. By the 2006 census, the population had grown to 132,641. According to oral history, Ejigbo is an ancient Yoruba settlement founded by Akinjole Ogiyan (a shortened form of Ogiriniyan), shortly after the establishment of Old Oyo. Akinjole Ogiyan was a descendant of Oduduwa and belonged to the ruling family of Ile-Ife.

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Egúngún Adanimodo has similar conical headdress like Egúngún Ìyékúyẹ of Imesi-Ilé but with bamboo sticks instead of feathers. Both shares powerful charms to secure their communities.

Plate 14: Egúngún Adanimodo of Ejigbo Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

Plate 15: Egúngún Owolewa of Ejigbo entertaining guest Source: Agbeleye Adesola (2025)

STRUCTURAL AND MATERIAL SIMILARITIES IN THE COSTUMES

Across all six towns, Egúngún ensembles display notable structural and material consistencies that reflect shared aesthetic traditions and spiritual meanings.

i. Layered Robes (Àgbàrá)

Each community employs thick, multilayered garments constructed from materials such as “àṣọ-òkè”, velvet, brocade, sequined textiles, embroidered cloth, and various handwoven fabrics. These layers symbolize ancestral depth, the accumulation of generational wisdom, and the spiritual protection surrounding the masquerade.

ii. Concealed Amulets and Power Objects

Embedded within the costumes are hidden charms (“ògùn”), which serve multiple purposes: protecting the masquerader, invoking ancestral presence, and reinforcing the spiritual authority of the performance. This concealed use of ritual objects is a consistent feature across all six towns.

iii. Headdresses and Mask Forms

The headdresses exhibit shared stylistic features, including domed helmet masks, elongated vertical structures representing spiritual elevation, and veils designed to obscure the masquerader’s human identity. Together, these forms emphasize the transformation from human performer to ancestral embodiment. Ile-Ifẹ̀, Imesi-Ilé, and Osogbo display some of the most elaborate masking traditions, reflecting their historical status as spiritual centers.

iv. Lappets (Jigida)

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Long flowing textile panels are a prominent feature of Egúngún costumes, moving dynamically during performance to symbolize the motion of ancestral spirits, the transmission of blessings, and the continuity of lineages. Ornamentation on these panels and other parts of the costumes includes cowries, beads, metal elements, appliqué designs, and a variety of symbolic motifs. Geometric patterns, animal imagery, and cosmological symbols point to shared cultural origins and reflect historical migration, inter-group marriages, and long-standing exchange networks across Osun state Yoruba society. These visual codes help reinforce a communal identity that extends beyond individual town boundaries, contributing to a broader sense of pan-Yorùbá kinship. Within a social realist framework, the aesthetics of Egúngún costumes communicate moral expectations, hierarchy, authority, communal values, sacred histories, and social prohibitions. In this way, Egúngún costume aesthetics operate as instruments of social discipline and cultural education.

v. Colour Similarities

Across all six towns, the colour palette of Egúngún costumes reveals strong shared symbolic and aesthetic conventions rooted in Yoruba cosmology and communal identity. Certain colours recur with remarkable consistency most notably red, white, black, and multicoloured combinations each carrying layered communal meanings that transcend local variations. The colour White (Plates 2, 3) is widely used as a foundational or accent colour, symbolising purity, ancestral presence, moral clarity, and spiritual cleanliness. Its prominence across the towns reflects the belief that Egúngún embody benevolent ancestral forces whose appearance must radiate both holiness and authority. Red colour (Plates 4, 9) appears frequently in cloth layers, appliqués, and trims, functioning as a visual marker of vitality, power, protection, and transformative energy. In Egúngún contexts, red often connotes the dynamic force of life and the spiritual potency necessary for ancestral intervention in human affairs.

Black colour, used in panels or structural base fabrics, signifies mystery, depth, authority, and the invisible realm of the spirits. Its presence across the towns underscores the masquerades' connection to the unseen world and its role as an intermediary between the living and the dead. Alongside these core colours, multicoloured layering, which is a hallmark of Egúngún attire, is found consistently across the six towns (Plates 11, 15). The vibrant mixture of green, yellow, blue, purple, and patterned fabrics symbolises abundance, the multiplicity of ancestral virtues, and the diverse blessings the ancestors bestow upon the community. These combinations also heighten the visual impact of spinning, lifting, and swirling movements during performances, reinforcing the dramatic embodiment of spiritual power.

Summarily, despite local stylistic nuances, the colour symbolism observed across the six towns reveals a coherent cultural vocabulary in which colour functions not merely as decoration but as a codified system of spiritual signification, reinforcing the sacred authority and communal relevance of the Egúngún tradition.

SOCIO-CULTURAL REFORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT THROUGH ANCESTRAL KINDRED-SHIP

The findings reveal that Egúngún traditions across the six Yorùbá towns display notable aesthetic and structural uniformities that reflect deep-rooted ancestral connections and long-standing intercommunal relationships. These shared features are not accidental; rather, they underscore a collective heritage shaped by migration histories, kinship networks, and cultural continuity. In the context of contemporary Nigeria where ethical lapses, social fragmentation, and weakened communal structures are increasingly evident the Egúngún institution offers enduring models for societal renewal and reformation. The embedded moral philosophy in these intertwined visibility provides frameworks for ethical reorientation, reinforces communal responsibility, strengthens cultural identity, and encourages conflict resolution. Through its artistic symbolism and functional display, Egúngún costumes act as a mechanism of social regulation and communal accountability. Therefore, the notion of kindred-ship expressed through Egúngún symbolism represents a culturally grounded pathway for meaningful social reform.

4. CONCLUSION

Egúngún costumes in Imesi-Ilé, Ile-Ifè, Ejigbo, Ede, Osogbo, and Ila-Orangun share significant aesthetic and symbolic similarities rooted in ancestral memory. Layered costumes, hidden amulets, headdresses, colour codes, and masking structures reflect centuries of cultural exchange and communal kinship. These ancestral memories provide a continuity essential for modern social development. Re-enacting these traditions not only preserves cultural heritage but also is a continuous reminder to strengthen, unite, and improve morality, and social resilience. Egúngún kindred-ship, therefore, remains a vital cultural panacea for contemporary social reform and continuity not only in modern Yorùbá communities but also in the extended society.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adebayo, R. I. (2015). The historical development and challenges of Islam in Ila-Orangun, Nigeria. *IJIMS Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Society*, 5(1), 1–28.
- 2) Adebowale, A. (2020). Egúngún performance and ancestral embodiment. *Journal of Yoruba Cultural Studies*, 12(3), 45–59.
- 3) Biobaku, S. O. (1955). The origin of the Yoruba. Federal Information Service.
- 4) Campbell, B. (2016). Cloth as Metaphor in Egungun Costumes. Retrieved on December 15, 2024 from <https://risdmuseum.org>
- 5) Eludini S. (2025) Personal Communication, c. 62 years, April 6, 2025
- 6) Oyeweso, S. (2002). Ede in Yoruba history. Lagos.
- 7) Pa. Tawode, E. S. (2025) Personal Communication, c. 81 years, March 18, 2025
- 8) Prince Adewale L. (2025) Personal Communication, c. 78 years, March 28, 2025